

SOCIAL MEDIA

MANASIJ MANDAL

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	525
1.1 Aims and Objectives	525
1.1.1 Aims	525
1.1.2 Objectives	525
2. Literature Review	526
2.1 Background.....	526
2.2 Facebook	526
2.3 Instagram.....	527
2.4 Twitter	528
2.5 WhatsApp.....	528
2.6 YouTube.....	529
3. Effects	531
3.1 Advantages	531
3.2 Disadvantages.....	531
4. Conclusion.....	532
5. References	533

List of Figures

Figure 2.1.1: Social Media526
Figure 2.2.1: Facebook market stock.....527
Figure 2.3.1: Instagram.....527
Figure 2.4.1: Twitter.....528
Figure 2.5.1: Whatsapp score.....529
Figure 2.5.2: Whatsapp status529
Figure 2.6.1: Youtube users530

ABSTRACT

Now that social media applications are available on mobile phones, it is not only feasible to communicate via this smart device but also to forge partnerships that will benefit numerous individuals around the nation and the globe. Nevertheless, despite all these benefits, there are still many gaps that negatively impact people's psychological, physical, and social well-being. Both benefits and drawbacks of social media exist. Because of this, negative things frequently occur on social media. Social media now makes it feasible for anyone to observe a wide range of terrible incidents. All that can be said is that social media should be used to promote worldwide harmony.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The man-to-man talk started in the ancient or can be said from the primitive age. As a result, people interact with each other, get to know each other, build relationships, and so many centuries of life have passed. After that, as people became more civilized, they closed themselves off in search of new things. After the primitive era, the primary communication medium was letters, letter writing started right but it took a lot of time to reach people by letter and more time was spent to get their reply, so this medium was time-consuming. Then came the invention of the telephone which was revolutionary, Graham Bell was the first to invent this device. This invention saved a lot of time that would not have been possible with letters. After that, a lot of time passed, and with the development of time, the telephone changed into today's smartphone or mobile phone. Now it is not only possible to talk through this smart gadget, but social media applications on this mobile phone have also become an opportunity to establish relationships for the benefit of different people in the country as well as the world.

A. Aims and Objectives

a) Aims

- Today's topic is about social media, here will be discussed about the impact of its use.

b) Objectives

- To find the creation on this platform.
- To research this topic.
- To discuss social media's effects.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Background

Social media has been around since its inception, there are various types of social media on this social media platform. Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Twitter, and YouTube all belong to social media (Barduset *al.* 2020). Facebook was first invented on February 4th, 2004, WhatsApp was invented on February 24th, 2009, Instagram was introduced to people in 2010 and YouTube was launched on February 14th, 2005. All this has completely changed our daily life.

This social media platform not only establishes relationships with people of the country and abroad but also shares various types of important information. Also, since photos and videos can be shared here, several people show their special talents in front of people, so that others can also show their special talents (Coyne *et al.* 2020). Every social media application has its capabilities, for which its demand has become high among people today. Many different types of social media platforms are used in daily life, some just for work breaks like Tiktok, Snapchat, etc. All these social media have advantages as well as disadvantages. All these are discussed in detail later.

Figure 2.1.1: Social Media

(Source: Created by self)

B. Facebook

Mark Zuckerberg was a second-year student at Harvard University, where he created an app that brought Harvard students together in an informal way. The name of this application is Facebook. Facebook was founded by Mark Zuckerberg in 2004 (Venegas-Vera *et al.* 2020). Slowly this application continued to make its place in the people of the whole world, and soon it became worldwide and all the people use it freely every second. Facebook was first launched as Facemash, later it was renamed to Facebook instead of Facemash. Mark Zuckerberg first created a website with his college roommates, including Eduardo Saverin, Andrew McCollum, Dustin Moskowitz, and Chris Hughes. The website was limited to Harvard University students only. It was later expanded to include colleges in Boston. It was then gradually expanded to colleges in the United States of America, and Canada. By 2006, everyone in the world had first set foot on the website with an email address verification system and a minimum age requirement of 13 and over.

Figure 2.2.1: Facebook market stock
(Source: Created by self)

C. Instagram

Instagram was invented in 2010 and its inventor is Kevin Systrom. The prototype of Instagram was called Burnbn. It was initially a photo and video sharing web application, through which, a variety of entertaining photos and videos were shared. Systrom loved Bourbon's whiskey so much that he named it Burbn. The Instagram application was launched on 6th October 2010 and as soon as it was launched, the number of users reached 25,000 in a single day (Dwivediet al. 2021). From the beginning, the main goal of creating this application was to post photos and videos taken by mobile. Kevin Systrom was a 27-year-old graduate student from Stanford University who started a free entertainment app. Kevin Systrom trained in computer science, and later started a company called NextStep, using the coding he learned at NextStep to create a prototype for Burbn. In the 21st century, Mark Zuckerberg created a virtual universe called the Meta Universe, although it is still under construction, this Metaverse includes Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp.

Fig. 2.3.1: Instagram

(Source: Created by self)

D. Twitter

Twitter was founded by Jack Dorsey, Noah Glass, Biz Stone, and Evan Williams. Now Twitter CEO is Parag Agarwal. On March 21, 2006, the Twitter application was launched, an online broadcasting medium that brought a particular form of blogging to the public. The difference between this microblogging and traditional blogging is that the file size of microblogging is small, so it does not require much space, but the files of all the blogging that are replaced by the traditional method are much larger (Mai *et al.* 2018). One can say that Twitter is a microblogging and social networking service in which users post various important or trivial things that serve as information. On April 25, 2022, Elon Musk bought Twitter for \$44 billion from Twitter's board of directors. Elon Musk's claim that the Twitter account has been hacked by various dishonest scammers has harmed people in the past and will continue to do so in the future. Board chair Bret Taylor disagreed with his comments.

Figure 2.4.1: Twitter

(Source: Created by self)

E. WhatsApp

WhatsApp application is one such application that has won the hearts of every people, for its little features. There's nothing like that, just messages, video calls, emojis, stickers, etc. So it is a favorite of so many people? All the other social media applications are full of advertisements, games, or gimmicks. But there is nothing special about WhatsApp and worst of all, it can be easily operated with the help of the phone's contact list (Pulido *et al.* 2020). WhatsApp was invented in January 2009 by Brian Acton and Jan Koum Yahoo former employees.

Figure 2.5.1: Whatsapp score

(Source: Created by self)

To begin with, there is no intention to turn WhatsApp into a messenger application, it is always designed to show someone's status like – “at the gym, busy at the office, phone battery low” etc. If we look properly, we can see that we put such messages in our status (Chatterjee and Kar, 2020). Acton then met with Koum and together they named WhatsApp, actually WhatsApp sounds like "WhatsApp", and on February 24, 2009, the actual WhatsApp Messenger was incorporated.

Figure 2.5.2: Whatsapp status

(Source: Created by self)

F. YouTube

Video sharing website YouTube. Steve Chen, Chad Hurley, and Javed Karim, three senior employees of US e-commerce business PayPal, bought the domain on February 14, 2005. They had the idea that everyone wanted to share their "home videos". San Bruno, California is home to the headquarters. An estimated 30,000 people a day visited the website when it went live on a limited ("beta") basis in May 2005. On December 15, 2005, YouTube officially debuted, generating over 2 million views per day on YouTube. By January 2006 this number had increased to nearly 25 million views. As of March 2006, the site had more

than 25 million films available, and 20,000 new videos were added daily (Pop *et al.* 2020). As of January 2006, a certain number reached around 25 million hits. As of March 2006, the site had more than 25 million movies available, and 20,000 new videos were added daily. YouTube produced more than 100 million videos per day in the summer of 2006, and the rate of video uploads to the website shows no signs of slowing down.

Figure 2.6.1: Youtube users

(Source: Created by self)

CHAPTER 3

EFFECTS

There are a lot of effects of using social media on our daily, there are some good effects and also bad effects. The below two points are discussed the advantages and the disadvantages of using social media.

A. *Advantages*

- Using social media is very much an important matter just like other work, we all are getting informed from any of social media in these days.
- From social media, we can know various news about the country and abroad.
- Through this, people can convey their creative thoughts to all parts of the world.
- Different types of job advertisements are circulated on social media.

B. *Disadvantages*

- Although everything is available on social, not everything is based on social media, excessive use of social media interferes with other useful activities.
- Social media should be kept away from children as much as possible, otherwise, there will be a lack of motivation in education later on.
- Nowadays various dishonest businesses open accounts on social media and embarrass people emotionally.
- Also, there are many opportunities for cybercrime from social media, even this cybercrime happens through social media.

CHAPTER 4

CONCLUSION

In this particular section, we will discuss the conclusion of the points discussed above. Social media was invented to bridge the distance between people, share information, unite, and temporarily brighten the monotony of everyday life. And all social media have succeeded in this task very well. Every person in the world is using social media, people are earning through social media in the 21st century. What was not possible to think at first has now been realized. However, despite all these advantages, many gaps remain, which adversely affect people psychologically, physically, and socially. Social media has many advantages as well as disadvantages. As a result of which something bad happens constantly through social media. A variety of unpleasant events that have become possible for people to witness are shown on social media. All that can be said is that social media should be used in such a way that peace is maintained all around.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Bardus, M., El Rassi, R., Chahrour, M., Akl, E.W., Raslan, A.S., Meho, L.I. and Akl, E.A., 2020. The use of social media to increase the impact of health research: systematic review. *Journal of medical Internet research*, 22(7), p.e15607.
- [2.] Coyne, S.M., Rogers, A.A., Zurcher, J.D., Stockdale, L. and Booth, M., 2020. Does time spent using social media impact mental health?: An eight year longitudinal study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 104, p.106160.
- [3.] Venegas-Vera, A.V., Colbert, G.B. and Lerma, E.V., 2020. Positive and negative impact of social media in the COVID-19 era. *Reviews in cardiovascular medicine*, 21(4), pp.561-564.
- [4.] Dwivedi, Y.K., Ismagilova, E., Rana, N.P. and Raman, R., 2021. Social media adoption, usage and impact in business-to-business (B2B) context: A state-of-the-art literature review. *Information Systems Frontiers*, pp.1-23.
- [5.] Mai, F., Shan, Z., Bai, Q., Wang, X. and Chiang, R.H., 2018. How does social media impact Bitcoin value? A test of the silent majority hypothesis. *Journal of management information systems*, 35(1), pp.19-52.
- [6.] Pulido, C.M., Ruiz-Eugenio, L., Redondo-Sama, G. and Villarejo-Carballido, B., 2020. A new application of social impact in social media for overcoming fake news in health. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(7), p.2430.
- [7.] Chatterjee, S. and Kar, A.K., 2020. Why do small and medium enterprises use social media marketing and what is the impact: Empirical insights from India. *International Journal of Information Management*, 53, p.102103.
- [8.] Pop, R.A., Săplăcan, Z. and Alt, M.A., 2020. Social media goes green—The impact of social media on green cosmetics purchase motivation and intention. *Information*, 11(9), p.447.